

Slaying of Husayn Texts

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A series of succession crises followed the death of the Islamic Prophet Muḥammad. One such crisis took place in the year 680 CE. Those who favored Muḥammad's bloodline believed 'Alī's eldest son Ḥasan (c. 625-670) to be the divinely appointed leader. Ḥasan capitulated to the Caliph Mu'āwiya in order to avoid bloodshed, but there seems to have been a tacit agreement that at Mu'āwiya's death the leadership would return to the Prophet's household. Ḥasan predeceased Mu'āwiya, leaving Ḥusayn as the supposed successor, but on his deathbed Mu'āwiya transferred power to his own son Yazīd. Unlike his older brother, Ḥusayn was not content to trade deference for peace, and in the 61st year of the Islamic calendar Ḥusayn and a handful of his companions met Yazīd's forces on the plains of Karbalā' on the banks of the Euphrates River in Iraq. The outcome of the "battle" was a foregone conclusion—according to traditional sources of this narrative Ḥusayn's band of a hundred-odd men, women, and children was several orders of magnitude smaller than Yazīd's army. Virtually all who fought with Ḥusayn died in a massacre which has thence served as the definitive event for Shī'ite piety. From relatively soon after the battle Ḥusayn's partisans have commemorated his martyrdom through a series of rituals, legends, and elegies which have grown increasingly elaborate through the centuries. This entry explores one type of pietistic commemoration—"maqtal al-Ḥusayn" texts from the late-Abbasid period when Twelver Shī'ism was crystalizing. These texts were compiled by three Muslims: 'Abdullāh Muḥammad ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī (d. 1172); al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn Ja'far ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Namā al-Ḥillī (d. 1247 or 1252); and 'Alī ibn Mūsā ibn Ja'far ibn Muḥammad ibn Ṭāwūs (d. 1265).

Date Range: 1150 CE - 1250 CE

Region: Karbalā' and its environs

Region tags: Middle East, Iran, Arabian Gulf

Location of Husayn's final days

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Maqtal al-Ḥusayn by al-Khwārizmī (d. 1172)
- Source 2: Muthīr al-Ahzān by Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī (d. 1247 or 1252)
- Source 3: al-Luhūf fī Qatlā al-Ṭufūf by Ibn Ṭāwūs (d. 1265)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Texts are compositions of oral and written traditions, some of which date back centuries.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: There are no extant original manuscripts of these texts. They are currently published by companies in Qom and Beirut.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: Holy sites in Islam typically feature calligraphy, but as noted above the original compilations of the maqṭal (slaying) texts have been lost to time.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The texts have quasi-canonical status and are used in religious practice, especially during the Shi'ite commemorations of the first 10 days of Muḥarram (the days leading up to 'Āshūrā', the day of al-Ḥusayn's death).

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The texts are written in Arabic, which has special status in Islam.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Many Twelver Shi'ites speak Persian, though Arabic remains the language of religious devotion.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

Notes: The texts are written in formal, Classical Arabic rather than in a local dialect.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

– Divinity

– Institutions

Notes: The special status of Arabic is found in the language of the Qur'ān itself, which states (Q 12:2), *إِنَّا أَنْزَلْنَاهُ قُرْآنًا عَرَبِيًّا*, "We have sent it down as an Arabic Qur'ān." Rich scholarship exists on the sacred nature of the Arabic tongue.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

Notes: Non-religious, as well as religious-but-non-Muslim, authorities historically have taught the Arabic language.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The duality between orality and textuality is not sharp in Islam, as oral traditions are frequently crystalized in writing with compilers taking special care to record the chain of transmission through which a given tradition has arrived.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 150000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 150000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 1

Notes: Individuals are encouraged to read the maqal texts for the sake of personal piety.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 500000

Notes: Hundreds of thousands of pilgrims visit Ḥusayn's tomb on the anniversary of his death, and maqal texts are used in their commemoration.

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Growth of Twelverism has led to increased audience sizes. However, sectarian and other violence in contemporary Iraq make the pilgrimage perilous.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 65

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 1

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 25000000

Notes: Twelvers make up roughly 65% of Iraq's Muslims.

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Decades of warfare and repression in Iraq have taken a particular toll on the Twelver population.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: Twelver Shī'ism is a subgroup of Shī'ism writ large, which itself is a subgroup within Islam.

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

Notes: While proselytizing is not prescribed by the maqṭal (slaying) texts, devotion to Ḥusayn's memory and cause is implicitly encouraged. The texts promise a happy hereafter for partisans of the Prophet's family and a decidedly unhappy one for those who take up arms against (or are indifferent toward) it.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

Notes: Q 2:256 states that "there is no compulsion in religion" (لَا إِكْرَاهَ فِي الدِّينِ). While the maqṭal texts do not explicitly cite this verse, they nevertheless consider the Qur'ān to be an authentic revelation of God's Word.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

Notes: Shī'ites, as stated above, are sincere in their devotion to the Prophet's family and earnestly desire other Muslims to be as well.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: Throughout the maqṭal (slaying) texts partisans of 'Alī are seen trying to persuade other Muslims to support the Prophet's household. In the maqṭal text, Muḥammad describes "two weighty things: the Book of God, and my lineage and family tree, the mixture of my water, my fruits. The two shall not be separated until my pool (ḥawḍ) is returned to me."

Reference: al-Khwārizmī, Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.239

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: During the 'Āshūrā' observances the audiences are moved to tears and other expressions of mourning.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– No

↳ On the reciter?
– Yes

Notes: Reciters of elegies, poems of lament, and maqṭal (slaying) remembrances are noted for their emotive performances; certain people are even employed to weep and moan in order to engender tears in the eyes of worshipers.

Reference: Borrut, Antoine. ““remembering Karbalā’”: The Construction of an Early Islamic Site of Memory”. *Jerusalem Studies in Arabic and Islam* 42 (n.d.). p.253f.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– No

↳ Is it read?
– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?
– Yes

Notes: The texts are intended to provoke emotion in their readers.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– No

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?
– Yes

Notes: As above, the maqṭal texts are part of a larger set of rituals, texts, and behaviors that facilitate mourning for the fallen Imam. Shī’ites weep for two reasons: (1) they are heartbroken that the Prophet’s grandson died a grisly death, and (2) they feel communal guilt for the fact that most of Husayn’s companions and supporters deserted him in his hour of need.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
– Specify: Gathered inside specially constructed buildings called Husayiyyas, Twelvers listen to

poems, elegies, and maq̄tal martyrologies along with watching ta'ziyeh plays that recount the Imam's final ten days of life.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Number of participants: 500000

Notes: This number is simply a soft estimate of the number of pilgrims who gather in Karbalā' for the first ten days of Muḥarram. However, much smaller gathering also take place throughout the Twelver world. From Indonesia to Lebanon, from Myanmar even to Jamaica, Ḥusayn is commemorated through street processions featuring banners called 'alams and funeral biers called tabuiks; these public spectacles oftentimes include men and women scourging themselves with whips and chains or cutting their scalps with blades in an effort to mingle their blood with their slain Imam's; others pound on drums, beat their chests, or even walk barefoot across coals.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– No

Notes: Typically the texts are read for large audiences.

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: Yearly

Notes: The 'Āshūrā' rituals take place during the first ten days of the Islamic month of Muḥarram, during which the Imam and his companions and family members camped thirstily on the plains of Karbalā' while diplomacy was attempted.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

Notes: Interestingly, the cataclysmic event of the Imam's slaying creates a world of confusion in which even firm Islamic precepts are called into question. The maqātil writers go as far as to cite poetry that claims that Yazīd's forces did not just kill Ḥusayn but also the takbīr ("God is greatest") and the shahāda ("there is no god but God; Muḥammad is God's messenger; 'Alī is God's vicegerent").

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja'far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-'Ulūm, n.d..

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– No

Notes: Traditionally during the performance of the ta'ziyeh plays the person playing the part of Ḥusayn reads from a script, whereas other actors have memorized their lines. This is done so that it will be obvious to the audience that this figure is merely an actor playing the part of

Ḥusayn rather than the Imam himself.

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– No

Notes: The maqṭal texts do not seem to challenge Twelver orthodoxy or combine it with anything else.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: The fast on the 9th and 10th days of Muḥarram parallels that of Ramadan, though the former one is not compulsory for Twelvers.

Reference: PennyAppeal. "Fasting in Muharram Experience the Virtues of Fasting on and Around Ashura". PennyAppeal, n.d.. <https://pennyappeal.org/news/fasting-muharram>.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: There are innumerable copies of each of the three books, but without significant recensions.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The three texts belong to the larger genre of maqṭal al-Ḥusayn, which itself is a subgenre of maqṭal literature writ large. For a comprehensive study of Ibn Ibn Ṭāwūs's collections, see Ethan Kohlberg's *A Medieval Muslim Scholar at Work: Ibn Tawus and His Library* (Leiden: Brill, 1992).

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: These texts encourage devotion to Islam's Holy Family, enjoining religious passion even if they are not properly scripture.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: Weeping for Ḥusayn is seen as part of the Prophetic sunna (tradition): Ja‘far al-Ṣādiq, the sixth Twelver Imam, declares: “If someone sheds (bakā) or makes someone else shed (abkā) one [tear], he shall go to Paradise. If someone tries to weep (tabakkā) [for us], he shall go to Paradise.”

Reference: Ibn Ṭāwūs, ‘Alī ibn Mūsā ibn Ja‘far ibn Muḥammad. *Al-luhūf Fī Qatlā Al-ṭufūf Wa-ḥakayat Al-makhtār Fī Akhadh Al-thā‘r*. Beirut: Mu’assasat al-A‘alamā li-l-Maṭbu‘āt, n.d.. p.10

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The texts presume knowledge of and adherence to Islamic law but are not fiqh treatises themselves.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Notes: The Islamic calendar does not change, but the texts place special emphasis on the first ten days of the month of Muḥarram, especially the 10th day (‘Ashurā’).

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

Notes: In the story, al-Qāsim ibn al-Ḥasan, Ḥusayn's nephew, married Ḥusayn's daughter Sakīna on the 7th of Muḥarram; he then died fighting heroically at Karbalā'

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

Notes: The texts paint the Imam as being hesitant to spill blood but see his self-defense on the battlefield as appropriate for the sake of justice. Ḥusayn was in Mecca when troubles began brewing. He did not want the holy city to be profaned by bloodshed, so he and a band of followers set out for Kūfa.

Reference: Mikhnaf, Abū. Kitāb Maqṭal Al-Ḥusayn. London: Shia Ithnasheri Community

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: Annual

Notes: Ḥusayn's passion is to be commemorated annually during Muḥarram.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Notes: Men and women alike participate in acts of self-harm and abasement during the festivities.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: 500000

Notes: As noted above, hundreds of thousands of pilgrims participate in the 'Āshūrā' commemorations.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

Notes: Fast-breaking is traditionally done with dates and water.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– No

Notes: Traditionally, several groups of Muslims are exempt from fasting; presumably this applies to the 'Ashurā' fast.

↳ Pilgramages?

– Yes

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– optional (common)

Notes: Unlike the Ḥajj pilgrimage to Mecca, the pilgrimage to Imam Ḥusayn's shrine (where his body but not his head is buried) is optional. Annually between several hundred thousand and a million Shī'ites make the pilgrimage.

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: The pilgrimage and the maqṭal texts serve a common purpose: facilitating the mourning of al-Ḥusayn b. 'Alī's partisans.

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

Notes: The maqṭal texts do not guide the shrine pilgrimages, but they do recount the events of Ḥusayn's passion (as do the dramas of the Muḥarram observances).

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– Yes

Notes: Shī'ites make pilgrimage on foot to Karbalā'; some sources claim that up to 20 million people take part.

Reference: Modarresi, Sayed. "World's Biggest Pilgrimage Now Underway, and Why You've Never Heard of It!". Huffington Post, n.d..
https://www.huffingtonpost.co.uk/sayed-mahdi-almodarresi/arbreen-pilgrimage_b_6203756.html.

↳ Is the maintenance of the routes guided by the text?

– No

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrims walk.

↳ Feasting?

– No

Notes: There are iftars connected with the fast days, though they are not as elaborate as those during Ramaḍān.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Ḥusayn retains his bodily wounds (bleeding, decapitation, mutilation) in the afterlife, which proves shocking to his mother when she greets him there.

Reference: Ibn Ṭāwūs, 'Alī ibn Mūsā ibn Ja'far ibn Muḥammad. *Al-luhūf Fī Qatlā Al-ṭufūf Wa-ḥakayat Al-makhtār Fī Akhadh Al-thā'r*. Beirut: Mu'assasat al-A'alamā li-l-Maṭbu'āt, n.d.. p.81

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, 'Abdullāh Muḥammad. *Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn*. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.239

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: There are physical features to Paradise (gates, a pool, a garden, a throne), but it is not spatially relative to Earth.

Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The afterlife, according to the maqṭal (slaying) texts, is eternal, though seems to exist in time alongside temporal events (e.g., Muḥammad precedes his daughter Fāṭima into Paradise, who in turn precedes Ḥusayn).

Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Cremation?

– No

Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– Yes

Notes: Bodies are to be ritually washed and buried according to Islamic custom. The parading of Ḥusayn's head to and through Damascus was scandalous.

Reference: Ibn Ṭāwūs, 'Alī ibn Mūsā ibn Ja'far ibn Muḥammad. *Al-luhūf Fī Qatlā Al-ṭufūf Wa-ḥakayat Al-makhtār Fī Akhadh Al-thā'r*. Beirut: Mu'assasat al-A'alamā li-l-Maṭbu'āt, n.d.. p.74

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– No

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

Notes: Ḥusayn's head remains forever detached from his body, both temporally and eternally.

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

Notes: Many supernatural events are associated with the Imam's dismembered head -- it recites the Qur'ān for weeks after his death, those who prod it mockingly are afflicted, and possessing it seems to be a bad omen.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Notes: Those who pilfer from Ḥusayn's corpse are met with bitter consequences. This occurs thrice. First, the meat from the vanquished party's slaughtered camels is inedible because it was rendered "bitterer than aloe," and other meat which the victors tried to eat "became fire" when placed in a cauldron. Second, the dyestuffs and perfume were reduced to ash when confiscated from Ḥusayn's saddlebags, and one woman who managed to apply some perfume "became afflicted with leprosy." Third, jewelry among the war booty turned into either copper or fire. In each case the very mundane is imbued with cosmic significance through a supernatural transition.

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja'far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-'Ulūm, n.d.. p.121

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

Notes: A mosque has been built on the burial site of Ḥusayn.

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: In one poignant narrative, Ḥusayn takes his infant son to the battlefield to shame his adversaries and show them the absurdity of their barbarism. Rather than grant Ḥusayn a reprieve, an enemy archer shoots the baby through the throat. Ḥusayn catches his son's blood in his hands and in anguish throws the blood up in the air; heaven catches the blood and not a drop of it hits the ground. Here God takes care of the infant's body on a chaotic battlefield where there is no reprieve for formal burial.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: See the above note about the supernatural funeral held for Ḥusayn's infant son.

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: Bodies are ritually washed.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: Islam strongly resists anthropomorphizing God, though the Qur'ān does speak of God's hands, feet, throne, etc. The interesting thing about God's throne for the maqṭal (slaying texts) writers is not that God would seem to have a backside and a lap but that the names of Ḥassan and Ḥusayn are inscribed on it (Ḥusayn's is on the right, where his grandfather's name traditionally is in Sunni sources).

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, 'Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-Ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.107

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

Notes: God transcends terrestrial and temporal categories in Islam, although for the maqṭal (slaying texts) writers God does not seem to be strictly impassible. Indeed, God seems genuinely affected by Ḥusayn's passion and demise. Nevertheless, God is more than a sky deity; God is "greater."

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No
 - Notes: A special status is afforded to ahl al-bayt, the People of the Household (the Prophet, his daughter, son-in-law, and two grandsons), and it is through their lineage that Twelver Imams arise.

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes
 - Notes: The ninety-nine names of God point to God's goodness, mercy, and perfection.

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: God is not as stoic in the maqal (slaying) texts as in mainstream Sunni theosophy. God is described as passionate, loving, angry, wounded, and responsive to temporal events. I suggest that divine passibility can be seen in five dimensions: suffering, passion, temporality, deference, and partisanship. A plain reading of the maqal texts suggests a deity who is passible in these five ways.
 - Reference: Perkins, Tasi. "the Thirst, and the Sun, and the Bleeding": Ḥusayn as a Passible Liminal Figure in Pro-ʿalid Hagiography". Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University, n.d..

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'ān (Q 2:32) describes God as "All-Knowing, All-Wise" (الْعَلِيمُ الْحَكِيمُ).

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The theodicy of Ḥusayn's death is an unresolved question for the maqṭal (slaying texts) writers -- in dying in a gruesome fashion, Ḥusayn seems to overturn the just ordering of the cosmos. One poet, cited in the al-Ḥillī's maqṭal text captures this sense of contradiction. He reports a line of poetry that aptly describes the theodicy with which the heavens and the earth wrestle passionately: "Al-Ḥusayn and his sons were defeated in battle / And this is a strange and puzzling thing".

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja'far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-'Ulūm, n.d.. p.127

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

Notes: Al-Khwārizmī, for example, refers to ‘Alī as the beloved (ḥabīb) of God.

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.16

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

Notes: Fāṭima's tears prompt the Prophet and the attending angels to cry out (taṣrukh) which in turn moves God to a remarkably un-stoic anger (yaghḍab) and the stoking of a special hellfire for the killers of Fāṭima's son.

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja‘far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja‘far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-‘Ulūm, n.d.. p.120

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– Yes

Notes: Herein lies a distinct difference between normative Islamic theosophy and the theological perspective of the maqṭal writers. In one popular tradition, the Prophet says, “Fāṭima is a part (ba‘ḍa) of me and I am a part of her and whoever hurts her (adhāha) hurts me [and] whoever hurts me hurts God.”

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

Notes: Shī'ites, especially the "extremist" ghuḷāt sects, have long been accused of worshipping 'Alī or one of the other Imams, though most Twelvers would resist the notion that veneration verges on worship.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: God seems in the maqṭal texts to be partisan toward the Prophet's family and its partisans.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: Ḥusayn says to his adversary: "I have seen [a vision] that dogs were biting me, and among them was a most sly dog, who was the most vicious of them in [attacking] me, and he is you [Shimr], and he was afflicted with leprosy."

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja'far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-'Ulūm, n.d.. p.97

↳ In dreams

– Yes

Notes: For example, on the battlefield Ḥusayn "woke up, startled and related a dream he had just had of the Prophet, who had told him, 'O Ḥusayn my beloved, you shall be coming to us soon.'"

Reference: Ayoub, Mahmoud. Redemptive Suffering in Islam. The Hague: Mouton Press, n.d.. p.111

↳ In trance possession

– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: God revealed the Qur'ān to the Prophet through an intermediary, the angel Gabriel (Jibrīl). Additionally, deceased religious specialists communicate with the living in the maqṭal texts. For example,

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: God speaks to the people through the Qur’ān, as mediated through Jibrīl and the Prophet. God has revealed Godself in similar fashions to other peoples through other prophets.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: In one narrative, "the Prophet carried al-Ḥasan on his shoulder, and Gabriel carried al-Ḥusayn on a feather of his wing, and they left the territory [of the Banū al-Najjār]. The Prophet (saas) said: "By God, I shall honor the two of you today the way that God Almighty has honored you in the Heavens."

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.166

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: Jibrīl interacts physically with members of the Holy Family.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: No specific limits are set on angelic knowledge; angels seem to know whatever God reveals to them.

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: In one story, the Holy Brothers are found arguing about whose penmanship was superior. When humans cannot give a definitive answer, God enlists Jibrīl Gabriel. The text reads as follows: Fāṭima said: "I shall judge between them, O Lord!" She had a necklace, and she said [to the boys]: "I shall unstring this necklace before you. Whichever of you takes more of its stones is the one whose handwriting is better." She unstrung it, and at that time, Gabriel was at the foot of the throne. God commanded him to descend to Earth and to divide the stones in half between [al-Ḥasan and al-Ḥusayn], so that neither of them would be offended. Gabriel did so, to honor them and magnify them.

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, 'Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-Ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.180f.

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– No

Notes: Punishment in the maqatal texts is ultimately God's jurisdiction.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: See above for examples.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

Notes: See above for examples.

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: Angels are frequently mediators of God's communication.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Angels are seen displaying tenderness, love, and joy.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: Angels cry uncontrollably at Ḥusayn's death, as do prophets, saints, Imams, and even the non-sentient creation.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: Thirst is a constant motif in the passion narrative, but it is restricted to humans.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The maq̄tal texts can certainly be read to view Ḥusayn as quasi-divine, but not in the sense of a demigod.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Djinn are said to mourn at Ḥusayn's death.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is the domain of God in the texts, although God listens to the intercession of members of the Holy Family on behalf of its partisans.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: Devotion to the Prophet's household (ahl al-bayt) is indicated for Muslims in the maqal texts.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

Notes: Those who display cowardice when presented with the option of standing by Ḥusayn's side. Divine punishment awaits those who stand idly by or fight on the side of Ḥusayn's enemy counterpart Shimr.

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī gives the following report of a special hellfire stoked for the killers of Fāṭima's son Ḥusayn: "The Prophet (pbuh) said: On the Day of Judgment, Fāṭima shall come forward in a group of her female relatives. It will be said to her: 'Enter Paradise.' She will say: 'I shall not enter until I see what was done to my son after my death.' It will be said to her: 'Look into the heart of the Resurrection.' She will look and see al-Ḥusayn (as) standing there without a head. She will cry out (taṣrukhu ṣarkhatan), and I [the Prophet] will cry out (aṣrukhu) at the sound of her cry (ṣurākh), and the angels will cry out (taṣrukhu) at the sound of her cry (ṣurākh)." The story continues... "According to one account, she will call out: 'O my son! O fruit of my heart!' God, praised and exalted be He, will be angry on her behalf. He will summon a fiery pit of Hell called Hab Hab that had been set alight a thousand years ago [and had burned] until it had turned black, [an inferno] which no spirit (rūḥ) enters, and from which no sorrow (ghamm) emerges. It will be said: 'Seize the killers (qatala) of al-Ḥusayn.' [The fire] will seize them, and when they are in its craw, it will whine hoarsely, and they will whine hoarsely in it, and it will gasp, and they will gasp in it, and it will groan, and they will groan in it. Then they will speak eloquently, saying: 'O Lord! Why has this fire been made for us before the idol-worshippers?' The answer will come from the presence of God, praised and exalted be He: 'Those who know are not like those who do not know.'"

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja'far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-'Ulūm, n.d.. p.120

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: The texts do not specify the degree of suffering.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Other form of punishment

–Specify: Shame is an everlasting punishment of those who betray the cause.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, those who loot Ḥusayn's corpse reap bitterness, and those who mutilate his severed head meet with misfortune.

↳ Political failure?

– No

Notes: Ḥusayn's political rival Yazīd ibn Mu'āwiya retains the Caliphate and the Imam's progeny never know political ascendancy.

↳ Defeat in battle?

– No

Notes: Quite the converse, Ḥusayn's ragtag army is massacred at the Battle of Karbalā'. Injustice prevails and the unjust go unpunished.

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: An older maqṭal (slaying) text, that of Abū Mikhnaf, reports that when 'Abdallāh ibn al-Ḥawza attempted to purchase the would-be martyr's intercession, "Ḥusayn made a supplication to God, 'O Lord, plunge him into the fire.' Upon this, his horse got restless and caused him to fall with his legs hanging onto the stirrup. His head was dragged on the ground, striking every stone and tree until he died."

Reference: Mikhnaf, Abū. *Kitāb Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn*. Edited by Mushtaq Kurji. London: Shia Ithnasheri Community of Middlesex, n.d.. p.142

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Ṭāwūs records the following narrative from a man named Ibn Riyāḥ: I saw a blind man who had witnessed the killing of al-Ḥusayn. He was asked how he had lost his sight, and he said: I witnessed the tenth of ten men killing him, but did not strike him or shoot at him. When he had been killed, I returned to my house and prayed my last ‘Ishā’ prayer. Then I fell asleep, and someone came to me in my dream, saying: “Answer the Messenger of God, for he is calling you.” I said: What business do I have with him?” Then he seized me by the collar and dragged me to him. There was the Prophet, sitting in the desert, with his arms bare. He picked up a spear, and there was an angel standing before him with a sword of fire in his hand. He killed my nine companions, and whenever he struck one of them, their souls were engulfed in flames. I drew near to him and knelt before him, saying: “Peace be upon you, O Messenger of God!” He did not answer me and remained for a long time. Then he raised his head and said: “O enemy of God! You have violated my female relatives and killed my descendants, and you have not preserved my rights, and then you have done what you have done?” I said: “But I did not thrust a spear or shoot an arrow.” He said: “You are right, but you have committed many dark deeds. Come close to me.” I came close to him, and I was all covered with blood. He said: “This is the blood of my son al-Ḥusayn.” He lined my eyes with the blood, and since that time, I have not seen anything.

Reference: Ibn Ṭāwūs, ‘Alī ibn Mūsā ibn Ja‘far ibn Muḥammad. *Al-luhūf Fī Qatlā Al-ṭufūf Wa-ḥakayat Al-makhtār Fī Akhadh Al-thā’r*. Beirut: Mu’assasat al-A‘alamā li-l-Maṭbu‘āt, n.d.. p.80f.

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: None

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Reward, like punishment, is the domain of the One God.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: The coming of the Mahdī (the twelfth Twelver Imam) is not emphasized in these maqṭal texts.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: The Battle of Karbalāʾ has apocalyptic dimensions, but realized eschatology is not present in these late-Abbasid texts.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Notes: Per Twelver belief, the Mahdī's occultation will end at the eschaton.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

Notes: The intercessions of Muḥammad, Fāṭima, and Ḥusayn play an important role in extending mercy to sinners at the last judgement.

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– No

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

Notes: There is a sense in which a just world order will eventually supplant the current corrupt one.

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: The maqṭal texts do not take a stance on this issue.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: Compassion is a basic property of Holy Family members, angels, and God; this is especially seen in the comfort extended to Fāṭima as she suffers the heartaches and injustices that befall her younger son. God, who is al-Raḥmān al-Raḥīm, "The Merciful, the Compassionate," seems to suffer at Fāṭima's pain.

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.166

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: Ḥusayn’s gentleness is seen throughout his time in Karbalā’, and the mercy he shows both to his enemies and to the women and children of his own camp is exemplary.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: The texts especially value charity and often depict Ḥasan and Ḥusayn as competing to out-give one another, with Ḥusayn once intentionally giving less than his brother in order not to be worthy of equal praise. He humbly states, "I am not as generous as my brother."

Reference: ibn Mūsā Al-Khwārizmī, ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.91

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: Volunteering to fight alongside Ḥusayn, as was the case with the general al-Ḥurr ibn Yazīd al-Tamīmī is seen as an extreme virtue.

Reference: Mikhnaf, Abū. Kitāb Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Edited by Mushtaq Kurji. London: Shia Ithnasheri Community of Middlesex, n.d.. p.92

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: Moral rectitude is of the utmost import for the maqṭal (slaying) authors, and no one is seen as more just than Ḥusayn ibn ‘Alī ibn Abī Ṭālib.

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Performing ritual ablutions is a virtue in the texts. Sensing her father’s impending demise, Fāṭima gently washes the sweat from his holy brow and helps him with the ritual ablution (wuḍū’). Sensing her own impending mortality, she makes one final ablution (prompting her friend Salmā to recount, “she washed herself as well as I had ever seen her wash herself”) and then lies down with her hands under her face oriented toward the Ka’ba in Mecca and dies peacefully “in a state of purity”—i.e., she is ritually immaculate.

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja’far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja’far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-‘Ulūm, n.d.. p.13

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.126

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Even more important than filial piety is piety toward the family of the Prophet. Particularly frowned upon is the Prophet's young wife 'Ā'isha, who looked with bitterness upon the Prophet's stock (Fāṭima). The animosity between these women plays out in numerous accounts in the maqāl texts.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: In one poignant story, two brothers who escaped Ibn Ziyād's soldiers encounter a woman and solicit water and a place to stay. The woman is fearful because her husband is in Ibn Ziyād's army. Nevertheless, she gives them harbor. When she brings sustenance to their hiding place they refuse it, asking instead for a prayer rug, following the model of the self-sacrificial Imam who elected piety over satiation. The younger says to the elder, "Brother, keep my company and smell my odor because I think this night will be the last night;" they then lock in a tearful embrace. In the meanwhile, the husband comes home in a foul mood; apparently Ibn Ziyād has offered him a ten thousand dirham bounty for the capture of the boys hiding in his home. His wife cautions him not to make enemies out of God and Muḥammad, but he brushes this off and demands his supper. While eating, he hears the whispers of the boys' prayers, grabs a lantern, and captures them. They make recourse to being relatives of the Prophet, but the soldier intends to claim his reward. He orders his servant to decapitate the brothers and offers them a reward for it but the servant fears God and refuses. Ultimately, the boys and the servant end up dead; the boys' decapitated bodies embrace one another as they float down the Euphrates; the river rejects the third corpse being thrown into it, so it is burnt. Loyalty to the just cause and fidelity to the Prophet's household are virtues in this story.

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, 'Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqāl Al-ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d..

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: The tens of thousands of Kūfāns who had pledged loyalty to Ḥusayn as Caliph eventually desert him, and the texts lavish praise on the roughly 100 companions and family members who stay by his side.

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: Ṣabr, or longsuffering, is a virtue associated with Imams, other righteous heroes, and even God, whose ninety-ninth Divine Name is al-Ṣabūr, “the patient One.”

Reference: Gardet, Louis. “Al-asmā’ Al-ḥusnā”. In *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition*, edited by P. Bearman. Brill, n.d..

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: The texts devote numerous chapters to describing the excellences of the members of the Holy Family, particularly Ḥusayn. Gabriel often testifies to this.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Notes: Ḥusayn stands up for justice rather than capitulating for the sake of maintaining peace with Yazīd, which leads to his death and eschatological vindication.

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Notes: Those with status, including the caliph and general of the Umayyads, are brought eschatologically low before God. These texts were written at a time when Twelverism was crystalizing, and the community's shared memory is of Imāms suffering persecution and falling victim to murder rather than achieving lofty political stature.

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: While in earlier maqtal (slaying) texts Ḥusayn bargains for his life to be spared, by the time of those being considered here he is seen as accepting of his fate. His anxiety is seen clearly in his response to the suffering of his family members, but he faces his own death reasonably serenely.

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Notes: Joyfulness is not so much a virtue as it is a reward for the righteous.

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Notes: Faith and trust, along with obedience and fidelity, are higher virtues than optimism and hope in the maq̄tal (slaying) texts.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

Notes: The texts do not seem explicitly to espouse gratefulness to a greater extent than the larger Islamic tradition does.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

Notes: Twelver tradition holds that Ḥusayn was in Mecca performing the Ḥajj when Yazīd signed his death warrant. Rather than allow his blood to be spilled in the holy city, thus defiling the sanctuary, Ḥusayn elected not to complete his pilgrimage rites—he preferred to be killed in a place which would not bring dishonor to Islam.

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Notes: Ḥusayn not only trusts God with his faith, but also trusts that his faith in God is well-grounded. He goes about fulfilling his mission with a sense of confidence that he is behaving in a morally upright way in resisting the unjust Umayyad government.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: While clearly valued, wisdom is not explicitly listed as a virtue in these texts more than it is in the Islamic tradition as a whole.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: Beauty is esteemed in a sense: the Prophet is acclaimed as, "Beauty of the Day of Resurrection (zayn al-qiyāma)."

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, 'Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maq̄tal Al-Ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.211

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Notes: Al-Khwārizmī's text does once speak of Ḥusayn bathing, but does so matter-of-factly.

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Enjoining virtue is itself a virtue. The tenth Imam, 'Alī al-Hādī, reportedly exclaimed of Ḥusayn, "Peace be upon you, O son of Fāṭima al-Zahrā'. I bear witness that you have performed prayer and given alms, enjoined virtue and prevented vice, and striven in the path of God."

Reference: Ibn Namā al-Ḥillī, al-Jalīl Najm al-Dīn ibn Muḥammad ibn Ja'far ibn Habatallah ibn Ja'far. Muthīr Al-aḥzān. Beirut: Dār al-'Ulūm, n.d.. p.13

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Ḥusayn had three sons, all named 'Alī, one of whom survived the battle to become the next Shī'a Imām after his father. Throughout the maqṭal (slaying) texts, having progeny is seen as good.

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Temporary abstinence is modeled by the Holy Family. On one occasion, Muḥammad asks God for a resumption of sexual relations with Khadīja after the couple has grieved the deaths of its children. God sends Gabriel down to reseal the union; the angel brings a plate of dates from the Garden of Paradise. The Prophet eats one, lies with his wife, and they conceive Fāṭima. From then on, says Muḥammad, "every time I kiss Fāṭima, I smell those dates. [That smell] shall be a part of her nature until the Day of Judgment."

Reference: Ibn Mūsā al-Khwārizmī, 'Abdullāh Muḥammad. Maqṭal Al-Ḥusayn. Qum: Dār Anwār al-Hudā, n.d.. p.111

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is expected of Muslims, though the texts do not spell this out explicitly. Interestingly, one of the most prominent motifs in the maq̄tal texts is not hunger but thirst

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Water is perpetually out of reach for Ḥusayn and his camp. For their part, the companions are unwilling to quench their thirst as long as Ḥusayn's remains: the leader of a midnight expedition to the Euphrates to fill water skins, Nāfi' ibn Hilāl al-Jamalī, is spotted by one of Ibn Ziyad's guards who bids Nāfi' "to drink to [his] health." Ḥusayn's companion refuses, however, saying "I will not drink a drop of it while Ḥusayn is thirsty."

Reference: al-Ṭabarī, Abū Ja'far Muḥammad ibn Jarīr ibn Yazīd. *Tārīkh Al-rusul Wa Al-mulūk* Vol. 19—the Caliphate of Yazīd Ibn Mu'āwiyah. Vol. 19. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 2015. p.108

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Notes: While not mandated by the maq̄tal (slaying) texts, there is a long tradition of mourners scourging and mutilating themselves in an attempt to mix their pain and blood with those of their slain Imām.

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: Some Shī'ites give a special tithe to their religious leaders, but the maq̄tal (slaying) texts do not

mandate this.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The texts implicitly urge devotees to mourn Ḥusayn's slaying on the battlefield and to observe the first ten days of Muḥarram as set apart for such mourning.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: As noted above, those who have "have performed prayer and given alms, enjoined virtue and prevented vice, and striven in the path of God" are seen as blessed in the maḡtal (slaying) texts.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: While the maḡtal (slaying) texts do not require their readers to be marginalized, these readers nonetheless have historically been marginalized vis-à-vis mainstream Sunnī Islam. The question of Ḥusayn's political legitimacy lies near the heart of the split between Islam's largest two denominations.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: While the texts may be read as part of personal devotion, they do not require such participation.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: The maḡtal (slaying) texts do not require such participation; nevertheless, they are used in ritual 'Ashurā' commemorations. Along with poems and elegies, they are to be read as part of the process of provoking devotees to mourning.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: While followers of Ḥusayn are not known as his siblings children, or other kinfolk, there is a blurring of genealogical relationships among members of the Holy Family. While he is the biological son of Fāṭīma and 'Alī and the biological grandson of Muḥammad and Khadīja, Ḥusayn does not fit a

single literary lineage very easily. At times he appears to be pre-eternal (see the next section on temporality); at other times, Muḥammad's son; at still others, Muḥammad's progenitor. Even his relationship to his older brother Ḥasan is in flux, especially when the question is raised as to who the greater of the two is.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: There are moments of levity in the narratives, and certain people are depicted as joyful and even as laughing at times, but the maqṭal texts seem to be intended to arouse somberness and sadness.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Individual religious scholars compiled traditions, along with their chains of transmission, into the maqṭal texts.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Later compilers have preserved the traditions in these texts along with their chains of transmission.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The texts are not intended for destruction.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: The texts do depict righteous people tending to sick members of the Holy Family, but do not institutionalize such care.

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: The texts do not specifically mandate payment of the zakāt tax, but the duty seems to be assumed. the Qur’ān (2:110) states, "establish prayer and give zakah, and whatever good you put forward for yourselves - you will find it with Allah."

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Notes: Ḥusayniyyas are locations in which Ḥusayn's martyrdom is recounted on the anniversaries of his birth and death. However, although martyrologies are part of this ritual commemoration, the texts being considered here are not specifically taught in these makeshift mosques.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The relationship between Islam and gender is too complex to be treated rigorously here. The texts do afford a special place to the women in Ḥusayn's life, notably his sister Zaynab bint ‘Alī ibn Abī Ṭālib and his mother Fāṭima bint Muḥammad. Of note, too, is Ḥusayn's daughter Sukayna (also known as Fāṭima al-Kubrā) who ordered al-‘Abbās to fetch water at Karbalā’ and supposedly initiated the SHĪ‘Ī mourning rituals (including elegies, lamentations, and dramatic poems).

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: In general, traditional Islamic education has been gendered, though this is not always the case.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: In terms of rewards, shedding tears in memory of Ḥusayn leads to blessing. Jaʿfar al-Ṣādiq, the sixth Twelver Imām, declares: “If someone sheds (bakā) or makes someone else shed (abkā) one [tear], he shall go to Paradise. If someone tries to weep (tabakkā) [for us], he shall go to Paradise.”

Reference: Ibn Ṭāwūs, ‘Alī ibn Mūsā ibn Jaʿfar ibn Muḥammad. *Al-luhūf Fī Qatlā Al-ṭufūf Wa-ḥakayat Al-makhtār Fī Akhadh Al-thāʿr*. Beirut: Muʿassasat al-Aʿalamā li-l-Maṭbuʿāt, n.d.. p.10

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: While not manuals for warfare, the texts revolve around a central battle in which a righteous remnant fights against -- and loses to -- a more powerful, insidious foe.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: As noted above, even before the defection of the opposing general al-Ḥurr, Ḥusayn offers him and his horse to drink from his dwindling supply of water and leads both groups in the appointed prayers. While not the same as mandating food disbursement, it does speak to Ḥusayn's generosity of shares sustenance resources.

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Reference: Specify: God is not as stoic in the maqṭal (slaying) texts as in mainstream Sunni theosophy.

God is described as passionate, loving, angry, wounded, and responsive to temporal events. I suggest that divine passibility can be seen in five dimensions: suffering, passion, temporality, deference, and partisanship. A plain reading of the maqatal texts suggests a deity who is passible in these five ways., Perkins, Tasi. "the Thirst, and the Sun, and the Bleeding": Ḥusayn as a Passible Liminal Figure in Pro-ʿalid Hagiography". Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University, n.d..

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